

Optimism and Mental Well-being among Adolescents: A comparative study

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Abstract

Optimism always leads to good and positive results in overall journey of life. It is the result of a process that keeps and improves mental well-being. There are many theories about how optimism works as a psychological phenomenon, such as "disposition," "attributional style," "cognitive bias," and "shared" delusion. This overview tries to figure out what "optimism" means and how it affects mental well-being. To understand why some mood and anxiety disorders make people more likely to get mental disorders, you need to be aware of both their positive and negative assumptions for the future. Optimism and ways of dealing with stress that focus on social support and the good things about the situation are strongly and positively related.

Background

In past studies, many psychologists have shown an interest in overlapping the areas of happiness, hope, coping, better quality of life, satisfaction with life, mental well-being, etc.

The purpose of this study was to find the best correlation between optimism and mental wellbeing, as well as how they affect adolescents. This study was done with 120 adolescent from Amar Singh College in Srinagar, Kashmir. They were chosen by the random sampling method from a group of 60 male students and 60 female students. Pearson's product moment correlation was also used to measure the relationship between optimism and mental-wellbeing. Because of this, we found a strong and positive correlation between optimism and mental wellbeing. There is evidence that students with a positive state of mind (optimists) live a better and higher-quality life than those with a negative mindset (pessimists) or low levels of optimism. Optimism may have a major impact on the student's mental well-being by developing a healthy mindset as well as behavioural adaptations linked with increased problem-solving ability.

Keywords-Optimism, Mental well-being, Adolescents

Purpose

This study enables us to explore the relationship between optimism and mental well-being among adolescents in Kashmir Division. Prior research focused on adolescents' quality of life, hope, happiness, and physical well-being as opposed to their subjective well-being. Positive psychology arose as a result of continued, concentrated efforts in these specific areas.

Methods

The findings from 120 students were included in the analysis, using the perceived stress scale, mental health inventory, self-efficacy questionnaire, and life orientation test.

Conclusion

Based on the literature reviewed, optimism is the tendency to anticipate favourable outcomes in the future. This viewpoint impacts mental well-being and the ability to deal with the stressors of daily life. Optimists are more effective at controlling their own life objectives and growth when they employ active coping methods, whereas pessimists are less successful at doing so. Hence, optimism is an important measure of mental well-being.

Introduction

Optimism is the anticipation that all future occurrences will result in a favourable conclusion. It is usually tied to people's future expectations; pessimism is the anticipation that undesirable and unpleasant things will occur in the future. Scheier

and Carver (1985) described "optimism as a generalized to expect positive outcomes even in the face of obstacle." It is believed that despite obstacles, one can achieve their goals. There was a distinction between a small and large amount of optimism. For instance, a higher level of optimism may help fight a disease and make the immune system stronger. It also helps in adjusting mood issues. But it can also depend on the choices made in terms of lifestyle. Psychologists have been examining the link between physical and mental health and optimism for many years and have discovered that the better a person is physically, the less symptoms of depression they report. Optimism is connected to confidence and positive mindset. Hence, adolescents and teenagers with greater optimism have greater confidence and the potential to do better in daily life. Optimism does affect feel-good hormones such as dopamine, serotonin, endorphins, and oxytocin. The level of these hormones is balanced by the way we think. We will be less likely to develop depression if we begin to balance our neurotransmitters. According to previous research, optimistic people find meaningful ways to achieve their life goals and deal positively with unfavourable circumstances. While doing so, optimism among the students can also turn the difficult present into a sense of good accomplishments and a bright future. Psychologists have studied the link between mental health, physical health, and optimism and have discovered

that those with strong physical health report less depressive symptoms. Since optimism is related with enhanced confidence or a positive outlook, optimistic adolescents will be more confident and mentally active in many aspects of life, such as indoor and outdoor activities, and more productive in their school work. Moreover, optimism has been linked to a lower chance of acquiring a variety of mental disorders. Adolescents with an excessively positive outlook find effective means to achieve their goals and deal with adversity. Optimism is the conviction that a challenging present may be transformed into a sense of accomplishment and a peaceful future. It comprises the belief that one's successes will be overwhelmingly positive.

If they were taught a clear set of goals and skills in an optimistic manner, optimistic adolescents would be ready to address their lives with flexibility and increase their general well-being. Trait anxiety is linked to a lack of optimism, which also has a significant influence on teen girls' school contentment as well as having a direct positive impact on school satisfaction through both internal and external motivation.

Current views on optimism

(a) Expectancy -value models of optimism

The assumption underlying expectation value theories is that most human attitudes, personalities, and behaviours are organised or arranged in the way they pursue their life goals. People tend to change their behaviours in order to get what they want while avoiding what they don't want. The greater the worth of a goal inside a person's motivation, the more essential it is to them. In the absence of a worthwhile aim, there is no motive to act. Anticipation is the second type of conceptual element in expectancy-value theories, and it is a feeling associated with certainty or uncertainty about achieving the best of their life goals. Most people will only act nicely and put forth their best efforts as their confidence grows. The most common expectation-based theories hold that behaviour is significantly predicted when the expectation level is congruent with the expected behavior. When confronted with a problem, optimists adopt a confident and persistent attitude, even though the progress is slow or difficult while pessimists are distrustful and timid by nature. Even in the face of extreme adversity, this divergence can be exacerbated. Positive thinkers believe that difficult times will pass and that it is only a matter of time. Pessimists always believe in the negative outcome, no matter how positive the current situation is.

(b) Dispositional optimism

According to Scheier and Carver, there is a worldwide expectation for more good things to happen than bad things to happen, or that the coming time or future will provide a plethora of

pleasant things but a scarcity of undesirable things. Optimism and pessimism are terms used to represent generalised expectations or expectations that apply to the entire life of a person. People fall into the category of exceedingly optimistic to extremely pessimistic, with the majority of people falling in the middle category. Dispositional optimism regards optimism as a personality attribute. It assesses people's expectations directly by asking them to rate how optimistic or pessimistic they are about their future prospects. In the current time optimism has received a large amount of attention and awareness among academic disciplines and scholars. According to Scheier and Carver 1985 "optimists are people who mostly believe that all good and positive will happen instead of bad." Generalized expectancy or dispositional optimism for positive and good future outcomes is an interesting resource in the present context for three reasons.

1. Optimist people are more liable or disposed than pessimists to find out a positive sense of
2. Benefit from adversity (Tennen and Affleck, 1998).
3. It is found that optimism is not related to rigid patterns of coping strategies, irrespective of stressor type. In fact optimism is related to flexible use of adaptive coping strategies with regard to the controllability of stressors (Solberg Nes and Segerstrom)
4. Optimism is considered as a predictor of perceived capability to manage the demands of a
5. Potentially traumatic events (Benight and Bandura, 2004).

Mental well being

The state of psychological well-being, a "healthy mental state," or independence from mental disorders is referred to as "mental well-being." It is a dynamic process in which a person's behavioural, affective, physical, cognitive, and social components interact functionally. Mental well-being is also a major determinant of one's integrated personality and balanced conduct, as measured by one's level of adjustment to oneself, others, and the environment. Positive emotions, a positive mental attitude, and pleasant behaviours are all part of mental well-being. As a result, a mentally healthy person is fully interested in his work, which can lead to outstanding performances.

According to the World Health Organization (2013) it is a condition of well being in which each individual fulfils his or her potential, can cope with typical life challenges, and works creatively and fruitfully." A person's lifestyle can influence their mental well-being, and mental well-being can serve as a bridge between lifestyle and health status. Many people regard their mental health issues as a social stigma and believe that they

will be shunned by society, which has an impact on their physical health and treatment attitudes towards mental health issues. Stress, lack of sleep, increased addiction to social media, hormonal imbalance, and low meal intake all contribute to adolescent mental health problems. People who have food insecurity are more likely to suffer from mental health issues. As a result, food intake has a direct effect on mental well-being.

Factors affecting mental well-being

Optimism, happiness, social support, coherence, and self-esteem are some significant positive factors that might serve as protective factors for mental well-being. These factors contribute to mental well-being. Loneliness, negative familial problems, low socioeconomic level, and substance abuse Sleep issues are just a few of the negative elements that can wreak havoc on one's mental health. Adolescents who have a poor form of mental health may also experience physical health issues. Sleep problems, lack of concentration, drug abuse, low self-esteem, and suicidal attempts are nowadays common issues among adolescents. Furthermore, adolescents with good mental health perform better in their academics as compared to those with poor mental health.

Optimism and mental well being

Understanding the susceptibility to mental disorders, particularly mood disorders, requires an understanding of both positive and negative future expectations. Recently, research has discovered a connection between optimism, depressive symptoms, and suicide ideation. As a result, optimism plays an important role in bridging the gap between these two concepts: hopelessness and suicidal ideation. Negative people, or pessimists, have less optimism for the future than optimists and are more likely to develop anxiety and depression, resulting in a lower quality of life and lower social functioning, according to new research. The impact of positivity or optimism on better quality of life was discovered in patients with somatic diseases, with a significant inverse relationship discovered between natural optimism and satisfaction level. Further studies have revealed a connection between depressive symptoms and optimism. As such, positive thinking or optimism tends to play a vital role in connecting the feeling of hopelessness with suicidal notions.

According, to the recent study of Vander Velden et al shows a great connection between "dispositional optimism" and depression in natural disaster victims.

Objectives;

- 1: Determine the relationship between optimism and mental well-being.
- 2: To find out the differences between male and female adolescents on the basis of mental well-being and optimism.

Research methodology

Sample size

The sample of the current study comprises 120 adolescents, including 60 females and 60 males Students from Amar Singh College 18 to 19 years old.

Tools;

1: Personal information Questionnaire.

It was designed to collect demographic information such as age, sex, religion, subject faculty, domicile, parent's education, family income, and existing family members.

The life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R) Scheier, Carver and Bridges, 1994) is a ten item scale comprising four filler item and six scale items. It was developed as a measure of optimism by adding the three items with positive and negative wording the LOT-R total scores are determined (these are reverse coded)

1. A four point scale with the response options "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" is used to gauge respondents level of agreement with each item.
2. An undergraduate sample internal dependability coefficient was reported by Scheier and Carver and Bridges to Scheier, Carver, and Bridges to be 0.78.
3. There were additional calculation for LOT-R optimism (the sum of three favorably written items) and LOT-R pessimism (the sum of the three negatively worded items)
4. 0.62 (for optimism) and 0.78 (for pessimism) were the internal reliability coefficients for these subscales (pessimism).
5. LOT scores are adversely linked with measures of hopelessness, depression, and self-esteem and positively linked with measures of self-esteem. A measure of optimism is the "Life Orientation Test-Revised" (Scheier, Carver, and Bridges, 1994). It consists of 10 items: six scale items and four filler items. The three items that are positively and negatively phrased are added to determine the LOT-R total scores (these are reverse coded).
6. Negatively with indicators of pessimism, depression, perceived stress, social anxiety, and signs of physical sickness.
7. Cohen, Kamarck, and Mermelstein's (1983) perceived stress scale (PSS) was developed as a stress indicator. The PSS evaluates the psychological stress that individuals reported experiencing during the previous month. Students rate each of the fourteen items on a 5-point response scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). The PSS-10's internal consistency and dependability, which were previously

greater than in.70, are now lower. Four studies were conducted to evaluate the PSS-10 test-retest reliability, and in each one, the reliability score met the threshold of $>.70$. As far as criterion validity is concerned, PSS was either moderately or substantially linked with the hypothesised emotional variables, such as depression and anxiety,

as evaluated by the Center for Epidemiologic Research. Among these are the Beck Depression Inventory, the State-Trait Anxiety Scale, the General Health Questionnaire, and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21.

Procedure

All the students were approached through the college's psychology department. A good rapport

was maintained with the students before starting the procedure. All were taken into confidence, and we were reassured about the confidentiality of their responses. Before sharing the Google form via online mode into the college group that was provided by college authorities, their consent for the test was also obtained.

Result

For obtaining results from both the male and female adolescent students on mental well-being and optimism, an independent t-test was also used. To observe the relation between mental well-being and optimism The Pearson product moment coefficient of correlation was used. The following table shows the results. Other results are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Table no 1 correlation between optimism and mental well-being and descriptive statistics.

Parameter`S	N	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Pearson`S Correlation Coefficient
Optimism	120	14.89	2.953	.325**
Mental Well-being	120	16.40	2.485	

DOMAIN	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATIO N	STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN	T	P
MALE OPTIMISM	60	14.38	2.681	.346	-1.907	.05
FEMALE	60	15.40	3.142	.406		
MALE MENTAL WELL-BEING	60	16.20	2.510	.324	-.881	.380
FEMALE	60	16.60	2.465	.318		

$t=1.67 (<.05; t=2.39 (p<.01)$ one tailed
 In the table no 2 we found that the mean score value of optimism for male students is 14.38 and female Adolescents is 15.40 respectively. And t-value on optimism is -1.907 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. p value indicates that there is significant difference between both the male and female Adolescents on the levels of optimism. Thus the mean value of male optimism is low as compared to female. It can be concluded that the male has less life orientation and female has high life orientation.

Thus the mean score value of mental well-being for male Adolescent is 16.20 and female Adolescents is 16.60 respectively .t value is -.881 which is in significant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is a significant difference between male and female adolescents in terms of mental well-being as well. The mean score for

female adolescents is high on optimism and mental well-being in comparison to male adolescents. So it is concluded that mental well-being is comparatively high in female adolescents compared to male adolescents.

Discussion

This study on optimism and mental well-being was conducted in college-aged male and female adolescents to determine the impact of optimism on mental well-being. Findings from the present study are discussed below. An insignificant difference between male and female adolescents on optimism and mental well-being was found. Male adolescent students in college scored lower on optimism and mental well-being than female adolescent students, indicating that girls are more optimistic and mentally strong than boys, and experimental evidence suggests that these are good

and positive feelings. Shared by girls are more valuable because they foster positive perceptions of their own self and others they are more social and have altruism effective conflict resolution skills, and physical health (Lyubomirsky King, & Diener, 2005).

The present findings are consistent with prior research study on optimism among adolescents (Chang & Sanna, 2003; Lai, 2009), predicted that students reporting a high level of optimism would be less likely to suffer psychological symptoms compared to those with low levels of optimism. This finding is of interest because few studies among junior college students have reported significant effects of optimism. Further, more possible explanations may report that optimism also affects physical health by making changes in the behaviours and cognitive responses that are associated with greater flexibility and problem-solving capacity.

The second objective shows that optimism and mental well being has a positive significant correlation. There is substantial evidence that people with positive mindset experience a better mental health and are less likely to get effected with psychological disorders. (Scheier and carver) 1985. Optimists use different coping strategies social networks, and report longer friendships than do pessimists; the social networks impact the mental well being of a person as stress buffer. (Cohen & Wills, 1985).

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